

Vasyl Stefanyk Precarpathian National University

Policy of Open Science

Preamble

The term "Open Science" is gaining more and more importance and influence in the modern scientific environment. It reflects the desire for transparency, accessibility, and collaboration in the process of scientific research, education, and innovation. Open Science facilitates the rapid exchange of knowledge, increases the efficiency of research processes, and makes scientific results accessible and useful to a wider audience.

The policy of Open Science determines that in the research space, in order to increase transparency and trust in science, it is important to exchange all research results, not just the publications.

The main values and principles of Open Science are declared by international institutions, particularly by UNESCO and the European Commission.

The implementation of ideas and practices of Open Science in Ukraine is also due to participation in such international projects under the Erasmus+ KA2 program as "Open Practices, Transparency and Integrity for Modern Academia" (OPTIMA) and "Open Science for Ukrainian Higher Education System" (Open4UA).

Vasyl Stefanyk Precarpathian National University, within the framework of the international project EDUC-WIDE (Expansion of EDUC capabilities for inclusive development of ERA), within work package No. 1 "Open Science: analysis and recommendations" and in order to further promote the support of the scientific community of the university shall participate in the formation of the European research space (ERA) and integrate the values and practices of Open Science into all of the main processes of the university through developing the Open Science Policy Implementation Plan as a supplement to the University Development Strategy for 2020-2027.

The plan for the implementation of the policy of Open Science at
Vasyl Stefanyk Precarpathian National University until 2027

	Step 1	Step 2	Step 3	Step 4	Step 5
1. Creation of the Open Science Expert Group (hereinafter the group)	1.1. Formation of group composition and distribution of roles	1.2. Conducting the first meeting of the group	1.3. Development of a work plan and division of duties	1.4. Launch of communication channels and an information platform for the dissemination of information about Open Science	1.5. Conducting regular meetings, monitoring the implementation of the work plan
Indicator	- an order to create a group	- minutes of the meeting - approved meeting schedule	- a detailed work plan - distributed tasks among group members	- website or group page created - information in social networks spreaded	- minutes of held meetings, - making corrections to the work plan if necessary
Responsible performers	The first vice-rector, head of the research department	The first vice-rector, head of the research department	Expert group on Open Science	Expert group on Open Science	Expert group on Open Science
Timeframe	November 2024	November - December 2024	December 2024	January 2025	during the period of activity of the group
2. Analysis of the state of Open Science at the university	2.1. Development of analysis methodology	2.2. Data collection, conducting surveys, surveying university scientists	2.3. Presentation of results and discussion at meetings of the Rectorate, Scientific and Technical Council, Academic Council		

Indicator	- a document was created with a description of the analysis methodology	- a description of the analysis of the collected data - survey results and their analysis	- feedback and suggestions received - resolutions and decisions Scientifically-Technical, Scientific Council
Responsible performers	Expert group on Open Science	Expert group on Open Science	Expert group on Open Science, Rector's Office, Scientific and Technical Council, Academic Council
Timeframe	January 2025	January-February 2025	March - April 2025
3. Training for university researchers, postgraduate students, etc. on Open Science, improvement of digital skills in order to use digital tools of Open Science	3.1. Conducting an analysis of the current state of awareness among scientists regarding the use of digital tools and platforms in the field of Open Science	3.2. Analysis of the infrastructure, available resources of European and national practices regarding the use of digital tools, platforms in the field of Open Science	
Indicator	- report on the performed analysis	- SWOT analysis	
Responsible performers	Expert group on Open Science	Expert group on Open Science	
Timeframe	May - June 2025	August - September 2025	
4. Development of networks of cooperation	4.1. Participation in international and national	4.2. Use of instructional methodological material of the	4.3. Conducting workshops, seminars, conferences on

with other educational institutions of Ukraine, organizations by international alliances: EDUC-WIDE (Empowering EDUC for the inclusive development of ERA)	initiatives to obtain Open Science implementation practices, exchange of experience,	EDUC-WIDE project (Expansion of EDUC opportunities for inclusive development of ERA)	Open Science
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Indicator	-signed cooperation agreements	- instructive- methodological materials of the EDUC-WIDE project	- the number of conducted events - abstracts of the conference, printing of articles, etc
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Responsible performers	Expert Group on Open Science, Department of International Relations, Scientific Library, Scientific Research Unit	Executors of the EDUC-WIDE project, Expert group on Open Science	Expert Group on Open Science, Department of International Relations, Scientific Library, Scientific Research Unit
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Timeframe	during 2025	throughout the entire period of implementation of the EDUC-WIDE project	October - December 2025
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5. Implementation of recommendations and expansion of Open Science practices at the university	5.1. Integration of Open Science in all aspects of the university's activities, as well as in administrative processes.	5.2. Development and implementation of policies and procedures that support Open Science in all aspects of the university's activities	
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Indicator	- provision of technical and administrative support for researchers	- approved local regulations legal acts	
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Responsible performers	Rector's Office, Academic Council	Expert group on Open Science, Rector's Office, Academic Council
Timeframe	during 2025 - 2026	during 2026
6. Assessment and monitoring of implementation practitioners of Open Science at the university	6.1. Analysis of the achieved results and comparison with the initial analysis of the state of Open Science at the university.	6.2. Development of a plan for further improvement and development of Open Science practices.
Indicator	- presentation of the report for discussion at meetings of the Rectorate, Scientific Technical Council, Scientific Council	- updated plan for further improvement and development of Open Science practices
Responsible performers	Expert group on Open Science, Rector's Office, Scientific and Technical Council, Academic Council	Expert group on Open Science, Rector's Office, Scientific and Technical Council, Academic Council
Timeframe	the first half of the year 2027	second half of 2027

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